
Microbial electrochemistry in bioremediation

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ABSTRACT

The persistence of environmental pollutants is frequently attributed to the absence of suitable electron donors or acceptors. This limitation in electron flow hinders pollutant degradation and remains difficult to regulate. Electro-bioremediation offers a promising solution to this challenge by enhancing electron transfer during biodegradation processes, while simultaneously reducing energy consumption and the reliance on chemical additives.

Water contamination continues to be a critical global environmental concern. The consumption of water containing elevated levels of harmful compounds poses substantial health risks. This abstract critically reviews current applications of electro-bioremediation for treating contaminated water, focusing on two examples: nitrate removal, as investigated in the EU ELECTRA project, and microplastic removal, explored in ongoing research within the EU NYMPHE project. Data from laboratory-scale and pilot-plant studies will be presented to demonstrate that electro-bioremediation represents a viable and sustainable approach for the remediation of contaminated sites.

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